

Democratizing Robotic Process Mining: Literature Review Summary

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Abstract. This appendix provides the result of the structured literature review as described in the paper titled "Democratizing Robotic Process Mining: A Conceptual Framework for User Actions, Tasks, and RPA Bots". A complete list of all included papers and the assignment towards the taxonomy categories is presented.

Keywords: User Behavior Mining · Robotic Process Automation · Robotic Process Mining · Ontology

1 Structured Literature Review Result Table

This appendix provides supplementary information to support the findings presented in the main paper, titled "Democratizing Robotic Process Mining: A Conceptual Framework for User Actions, Tasks, and RPA Bots". The appendix contains the description of the structured literature review (SLR) as presented in the original publication as well as a complete list of all included publications in the following table.

This table provides a comprehensive reference list for all publications included in the structured literature review, which served as the foundation for developing the intuitive taxonomy presented in this work. The publications are grouped based on the specific action types they support within user interfaces (UI). For a detailed explanation of each taxonomy category and its associated action types, we refer readers to the original publications.

Table 1. Publications included in SLR ordered by taxonomy

Publication	Opening	Closing	Navigating	Concluding	Transferring	Transforming	Physical System Action	Empty Action
[1,2,3,13,28,29,31,37]			x		x	x		
[5,7,8,9,14,15,43]	x	x	x	x	x	x		
[11,17,23,35]			x					
[21,32,40,42,45]			x			x		
[25,46]			x	x		x		
[18,20]						x		
[26,30]				x	x	x		x
[4]	x				x	x		
[6]	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
[10]		x	x		x	x		
[12]	x		x			x		
[16]			x	x	x	x		
[19]			x	x				
[22]			x	x				
[24]	x	x	x			x		
[27]				x				
[33]				x				
[34]		x	x					
[36]	x	x	x				x	
[38]			x	x				
[39]				x				
[41]	x	x	x	x				
[44]	x				x			
[47]	x		x					
[48]		x						
[49]	x		x	x		x		
[50]	x							

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